

THE ARTISTIC AND PHILOSOPHICAL EXPRESSION OF THE CREATIVE PERSONALITY AND AESTHETIC CONCEPTION IN SHUKUR KHOLMIRZAYEV'S ESSAYS

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Abstract. *In the essays of Shukur Kholmirezayev, a prominent representative of Uzbek literature, the artistic and philosophical expression of the creative personality and its aesthetic conception stands out for its distinctive character. In the writer's works in the essay genre, the authorial "I," his attitude toward life, society, and art, as well as the philosophical foundations of his creative thinking, are analyzed. This article explores, from a literary-theoretical perspective, the essayistic style of Shukur Kholmirezayev, the subjectivity inherent in his artistic thinking, the role of inner experience, and the formation of his aesthetic views. The study reveals the moral position of the creative personality in the writer's essays, his attitude toward national and universal values, and his conceptual ideas expressed through artistic and philosophical generalizations.*

Keywords: *essay genre, creative personality, aesthetic conception, artistic and philosophical thinking, authorial "I," literary views, national and universal values, artistic thinking, essayistic style.*

Introduction

The development of the essay genre in Uzbek literature during the period of independence created a necessity to study the creative personality of the writer, their aesthetic views, and artistic-philosophical thinking. In this process, the writer's attitude toward life, society, and art, personal worldview, and aesthetic conception began to manifest directly through literary texts. In particular, the essay genre occupies an important place in the evolution of literary thought due to the active presence of the authorial "I," subjectivity, and reliance on philosophical reflection. In Uzbek literature, the essay genre acquires special artistic and aesthetic significance in the works of Shukur Kholmirezayev, one of its most mature representatives. The writer's essays are noteworthy not only for their engagement with the literary process but also for their exploration of significant philosophical issues such as humanity, society, national identity, creativity, and responsibility. In Kholmirezayev's essay writing, the creative personality is revealed through the author's position, while his aesthetic views are expressed through artistic and philosophical generalizations.

Although Shukur Kholmirezayev's prose—particularly his short stories and novellas—has been widely studied, the artistic and philosophical expression of the creative personality and aesthetic conception reflected in his essays has not yet been comprehensively examined. Therefore, this article analyzes, on a scientific and theoretical basis, the artistic expression of the authorial "I," the sources of the formation of his aesthetic thinking, and its philosophical content, drawing on the writer's works in the essay genre. Shukur Kholmirezayev's essayistic heritage (such as "Look Ahead and Back" – "Reflections on the Purpose of Society, That Is, Ideology," and the articles and essays included in "Difficult Roads!" – "The Hero's Final Days") is closely

connected with his literary works and serves as a key to understanding the writer's creative laboratory and his views on "harsh realism."

In Kholmirezayev's essays, the mission of literature, the writer's responsibility, and the concept of truth occupy a central place. The author emphasizes that "truth is the soul of literature." His memoir-essays about Abdulla Nabiyeu, Shuhrat, Odil Yoqubov, and Ro'zi Choriyeu are not merely biographical accounts but are aimed at analyzing the aesthetic roots of national literature. In artistic creativity, the essay functions as a kind of reconnaissance genre, similar to the sketch. However, this should not lead to the conclusion that the essay is a superficial or experimental genre. On the contrary, the essay is a complex genre built upon philosophical and analytical reflections and diverse considerations. In Shukur Kholmirezayev's work, the essay often serves as a stepping stone toward large-scale literary creations. For instance, after first writing the essay "Difficult Roads" about A. Nabiyeu, the author later created the novella "The Hero's Final Days," followed by the novel "Qil Ko'prik" and the drama "Qora Kamar."

The foundation of the essay "Reflections on Ideology" is the work "Look Ahead and Back." This is because "Look Ahead and Back" uses an epigraph from the *Avesta* concerning the creation of Bactria. In both essays, the ancient past, history, and the present are compared, and the author's personal viewpoint appears as the main protagonist. In "Look Ahead and Back," narration from the perspective of the authorial "I" predominates, which constitutes one of the key principles of the essay: "One great writer once said that acting with reference to the past and weighing history carefully is a virtuous deed. Without knowing whether it was virtuous, I became interested in the past, and in my heart arose a desire to connect it with the present day" [3, p. 64]. In the essay "Reflections on Ideology," the writer adopts a different mode of narration from the perspective of the "I." Just as Alisher Navoi narrates from the perspective of "kamina" in *Mahbub ul-qulub*, Shukur Kholmirezayev develops a similar essayistic style:

"It is natural that the initial emergence of the ideology of goodness should interest any sincere person. I, too, was drawn to this interest and cast a glance at the primitive—more precisely, tribal—periods of humanity, and involuntarily the land of Turan, where my own umbilical blood was shed, appeared before my eyes..." [4, p. 64]. In the essay text, Kholmirezayev does not narrate solely in the first-person singular "I," but rather shifts to the first-person plural "we." For example: "When we speak of ideology being connected with religion, yet not always subordinate to it, and even capable of denying it at times, when we speak of the emergence of ideology in human life..." [4, p. 64]. In both essays, the essayist addresses not only the reader but also himself. In "Look Ahead and Back," the writer recounts national traditions and values through childhood memories, including rituals related to mourning, the cooking of sumalak, the performance of the Boychechak song, Uzbek wrestling, and tales about Tiniqoy Granny and Hazrat Ali. Regarding these elements, the author presents two or three different reflections, offering multifaceted interpretations.

For instance, in the tale about "Tiniqoy Kampir," the song sung in lament — "Even if he were a bear, he was my husband; even if he were a bear, he was my child..." — prompts the writer to express two paradoxical interpretations. The first is that "this legend was created during the Islamic period. A woman must submit to her husband and should not separate from him regardless of who he is..." [3, p. 205]. The second interpretation states: "In my view, even in the song Tiniqoy sings in sorrow for her 'bear husband,' the closeness of humans to nature finds its expression" [3, p. 205]. These two perspectives offered by the writer are open to debate. In the first interpretation, the elevated, almost semi-divine status of the husband in Muslim societies is indeed accurately reflected. However, in the second interpretation, the essayist advances a much broader paradox. In

general, while agreeing with Sh. Kholmirezayev's paradoxical reflections on the meaning expressed in Tiniqoy Kampir's mournful song, we would emphasize that the song primarily conveys the terrible anguish of loneliness. This is because after Tiniqoy Kampir's brothers went into the forest, killed her bear husband, and brought her back to the village, she has lived a life of utter solitude. The people refuse to seek her hand in marriage because she had once married a bear.

What is particularly important is that in both essays Sh. Kholmirezayev connects his childhood observations with scholarly knowledge. Thus, within a single essay, streams of philosophical, scientific, artistic, publicistic, and lyrical-monologic reflections frequently alternate. The essayist's reflections on the *Avesta* and Zoroastrianism are further developed in the essay "*Reflections on the Purpose of Society, That Is, Ideology.*" "*Smell the Violets, Uncle*" is one of the author's most substantial essays. Initially, the essay was written about O'lmas Umarbekov. Regarding this, Sh. Kholmirezayev notes: "*Naturally, under the pretext of Umarbekov, I unknowingly infused the essay with my thoughts about those talents as well, and about the generation of the 1960s in general—more precisely, about the process of their formation*" [8, p. 3]. Indeed, this series of essays organically demanded continuity. Overall, the cycle consists of four essays: "*Smell the Violets, Uncle*" (about O'lmas Umarbekov), "*On the Roads of Fergana*" (about U. Nazarov), "*A Warm Soul*" (about Sh. Kholmirezayev and A. Oripov), and "*Smell the Violets, Uncle*" (about B. Zokirov). In all of them, the image of O'lmas Umarbekov occupies a central position.

The title "*Smell the Violets, Uncle*" itself has a distinct history. In the first essay of the cycle, a critical discussion takes place between O'lmas Umarbekov and Sh. Kholmirezayev concerning the short story "*The Flower Girl.*" The phrase "*Smell the violets, uncle,*" taken from Umarbekov's speech during that conversation, became the basis for the essay's title. When Sh. Kholmirezayev points out the implausibility of a particular episode in the story, Umarbekov responds that he was attempting to create his own artistic and aesthetic ideal. Incidentally, the violet carries symbolic meaning: it represents the awakening of a nation that lies in heedlessness. Making effective use of this artistic and aesthetic symbol, Sh. Kholmirezayev titles his memories of the generation of the 1960s "*Smell the Violets, Uncle.*"

In the essay "*Smell the Violets, Uncle,*" representatives of the intellectual elite—writers, poets, composers, television engineers, directors, and actors—appear as literary characters (including U. Nazarov, O'lmas Umarbekov, F. Musajonov, A. Oripov, O'. Hoshimov, composer M. Burhonov, actor T. Azizov, and pop singer B. Zokirov). Their psychological states, creative cooperation, and attitudes toward the past and the future are described in detail. The direct participant in the events is the writer himself; however, he does not recount events blindly. The author pays close attention even to the most subtle and invisible inner psychological processes of the human soul. He seeks to rediscover both the inner and outer worlds of each character.

The writer objectively depicts the relationships among his creative peers, as well as their views on society and literary life. In the essay dedicated to O'lmas Umarbekov, the author's artistic intention is to demonstrate the efforts of the generation of the 1960s—who, while striving to introduce their nation to the world, also sought to defend national pride, honor, and dignity. With this aim, the essayist recounts meetings, conversations, gatherings, and creative journeys of the intellectual elite. In their conversations, a sense of dissatisfaction with the existing social order becomes evident. This is especially noticeable during the recitation of A. Oripov's poem "*The Nightingale*":

“As I observed, this symbolic (and at the same time realistic) poem bestowed ironic smiles upon the participants of the gathering and brought them closer together, as if ‘nightingales’ were sitting in the circle, intuitively understanding one another without words” [5, p. 5].

Sh. Kholmirezayev closely observes the modern Uzbek intellectual and seeks—even in small measure—national qualities within them. It is no secret that during the 1960s–1970s, imitation of Russian culture was at its peak among our people: clothing styles, behavior, manners of speech, and everyday conduct all underwent Russification. The cycle of essays “*Smell the Violets, Uncle*” resembles a work of elite literature, as the dialogues among the characters are confined to a specific professional sphere—primarily discussions about creativity. Not only literary creation, but also cinema, music, and theater are debated by the characters.

For some readers, the processes and events depicted in the work may seem tedious or difficult to understand. However, the essayist artistically reveals not only the creative but also the ordinary human faces of intellectuals who were determined to elevate national pride—their sufferings, personal tragedies, and moments of ascent unique to each individual. In studying the characters, the author appears as an objective observer; in certain moments, he assumes the role of a character-image, and in the final pages, the essayist himself rises to the level of the main protagonist. Thus, at the beginning of the work he is an objective observer, while in the section devoted to Uchqun Nazarov he becomes a far more active character.

Conditionally, the writer’s direct participation in the essay may be expressed through the following formula: **pure author** → **author-narrator** → **author-character image** → **author-main protagonist**. This formula alternates in various forms throughout “*Smell the Violets, Uncle*.” The central figure of the essay, the writer O‘lmas Umarbekov, is portrayed from the opening pages to the end as a gentle-natured individual who unites the generation of the 1960s and enjoys great respect among his peers. Uchqun Nazarov’s dual image—as a director in cinema and as a literary figure in artistic creation, combined with his sharp and resolute character—is narrated in the events of “*On the Roads of Fergana*.”

A striking feature of this cycle of essays is the excessive use of Russian words in the characters’ dialogues. This is particularly evident in the speech of figures such as O‘lmas Umarbekov, Uchqun Nazarov, Botir Zokirov, and Mutal Burhonov. This, however, reflects Sh. Kholmirezayev’s deliberate objective style. The historical period and social environment exerted a strong influence on the generation of the 1960s: they were educated in Russian schools from childhood, and communication in Russian became prevalent within families, among friends, and in public spaces. Fully aware of this reality, the essayist presents their jargon, dialects, and foreign linguistic elements to the reader without alteration. To substantiate this observation, let us consider an excerpt from a conversation between Shukur Kholmirezayev and Botir Zokirov:

“-I liked the story,” I said. That’s it. How you take it, it’s up to you.

- Really?

- Yes” [5, 3].

Or from O‘lmas Umarbekov’s speech: “...Nizom, Abdullajon, make one book for us too, like U. Nazarov’s. We will pray. Botir, chto s toboy?” [5, 3].

The essay about “Botir Zokirov” begins with a late-night phone call due to his death. That is, the essay starts directly with the resolution. The untimely night phone call gives the work a tragic pathos. In particular, “I woke up from the phone ringing... looked at the clock. Half past four... Naturally, I got angry: who is it – disturbing me at such a time? If it were from the village: let there be peace...” [5, 5]. Naturally, the reader encountering such an extraordinary situation

becomes interested in the continuation of the work. It provokes interest in the effect of this tragedy on the famous singer's family and friends. Following the principles of objectivity and truthfulness inherent in the essay genre, the essayist openly recounts Botir Zokirov's intimate relationships as well. In the literary portrait of this character, the light and dark, the sublime and tragic moments of life collide. This is due to the singer's innate unique talent combined with the severe suffering he experienced. Despite a harsh fate, the hero finds strength, courage, and will to live, and his life worthy of teaching lessons deeply moves the reader.

The plot of the essay "Warm Soul" encompasses two separate, intertwined narrative lines. The first concerns Sh. Kholmirezayev's hospitalization and the visit of friends, and the second concerns Abdulla Oripov's hospitalization and the comic events related to the visit of friends. In the essay, characters speak only in jargon specific to themselves. In particular, in the following conversation, through metonymy, the reader understands the creator jokingly putting a small cup under a larger one:

"-People are waiting. Someone came saying 'My love-my love.' The guide got lost, so I brought them myself! Padyom" [6, 4].

"People" refers to the author Uchqun Nazarov, "My love-my love" to the author O'lmas Umarbekov, and the guide role was performed by actor Turg'un Azizov. The character of their close friend, doctor Anvar Maqsadov, is also included because he was a close friend of the creators. One of the remarkable features of the essayist's style in this series is the painstaking depiction of even the smallest details. In this regard, in X. Do'stmuhammedov's dissertation "The Renewal of Artistic Thinking in Contemporary Uzbek Prose," it is noted that the writer Sh. Kholmirezayev employs a detailed descriptive principle in analyzing his recent stories. This observation is fully applicable to Sh. Kholmirezayev's essays. The writer sometimes provides explanatory notes in parentheses about people or even minor objects. For example, "I looked at the clock on the wardrobe (which Umarbekov gave me for my birthday)" – Sh. Kholmirezayev explains the clock he looked at in the middle of the night, even who gave it. Undoubtedly, this emphasizes the sincere friendship between the essayist and O'lmas Umarbekov. There are many such instances in the essay: "Botir came to our house (he lived behind the conservatory, and we were on this side of the road...) ... and I was talking with Botir's very respectful wife Erkli Malikboyeva about literature (she especially liked Paustovsky) ...", "We went to To'lan Qo'ziboyev's ('Tabassum' old editor) wedding", "The next day, naturally, Turg'un Azizov at the wheel (the car was Umarbekov's)...", etc.

Another feature of Sh. Kholmirezayev's style is the vivid depiction of the characters' actions as if they are happening right now. For example: "While I was trembling, not knowing what to do, my wife rubbed her eyes and came out from the bed, pressing her forehead" [7, 5]. One could say: "My wife woke up from the phone call and got out of bed" – but in such an expression, the disorderly, frightening state of the middle of the night would not be conveyed. The impact on the reader would be reduced. It is natural for someone sleeping to come out with forehead pressing, blinking, and a sleepy voice after a late-night phone call. The common theme of the essay series "*Smell the Violet, Uncle*" is sincere friendship. The essays depict various life events about the close friendships among Uchqun Nazarov, Shukur Xolmirzayev, O'tkir Hoshimov, Nizom Komilov, Turg'un Azizov, Anvar Maqsadov, and Abdulla Oripov. However, the unifying figure, the guiding one, is undoubtedly O'lmas Umarbekov. This figure does not always occupy the central position in all the essays, but certainly participates in the resolution or climax of the essay, in the author's memories. For this reason, Sh. Kholmirezayev calls this work essays about O'lmas

Umarbekov. Perhaps this is also due to his personal sympathy. But rightly speaking, these essays convey a great educational and moral idea: in good and bad days, a true friend must certainly be a support for one another.

In the essay “*Northern Radiance*”, the contradictory life of Surkhandarya journalist and writer Zoyirjon Mamajonov is portrayed. The North, being a place of white snow and ice, is likened to radiance and purity. In this sense, Sh. Kholmirezayev likens his hero to northern radiance. As if he attracts others like pure feelings and wishes.

Conclusion

In Sh. Kholmirezayev’s essays, as in Nasr, laconicism, sharpness, and sincerity prevail. He explains complex theoretical issues simply but deeply through life examples and personal experience. Writing about other creators, he seeks to reveal the spiritual image of the nation through their personality and work. The subjectivity characteristic of the essay genre (the author’s “I”) is harmonized with life experience. He places not only the achievements but also the spiritual sufferings of the creators he admires at the center of analysis. Sh. Kholmirezayev’s essays oppose “embellishment” and “artificiality” found in Uzbek prose. His literary-critical essays have been elevated to the level of a methodological guide for Uzbek literary studies. Overall, the principles expressed in the essays (truthfulness, logic of character, purity of language) are reflected artistically in his prose works.

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